

DSM_OPT

DEMAND SIDE MANAGEMENT: OPERATION OPTIMISATION OF INDUSTRIAL ENERGY SYSTEMS

DELIVERABLE 7.1 FEATURE IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

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PROJECT MANAGEMENT

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DELIVERABLE 7.1: FEATURE IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

To ensure the transfer of knowledge and the future application of insights gained from DSM_OPT, Task 7.2 developed a roadmap for the future development of DSM DSS toolboxes, which includes also a rough timeline, to estimate the needed time for the overall development and implementation.

This roadmap comprises the necessary steps to successfully implement a DSM DSS system at an industrial site. As industrial sites are heterogenous, even within an industrial sector, this roadmap won't point out case-specific details but will give an overview of the necessary tasks to execute. The roadmap is displayed in a graphical manner in Figure 1 and will be described in the following subsections. Concluding, we address the temporal factor: On the one hand, how much time should be scheduled for the individual tasks and, on the other, in what order they should be arranged in order to drive development forward as efficiently as possible. At this point, it should also be mentioned that the tasks cannot be considered decoupled from each other, as the development of a DSM DSS system is an extremely complex task. The arrows in Figure 1 are intended to illustrate which tasks build on each other and between which tasks feedback loops are necessary.

Figure 1: Roadmap for DSM DSS toolbox development at an industrial site

1 Foundation

The Foundation phase is critical for laying the groundwork of the DSM DSS system, encompassing three essential tasks: Process Analysis, Data Analysis, and Process Modelling.

1.1 Process Analysis

Process Analysis begins with a thorough examination of the existing production processes. This includes also data measurement and preparation, which may involve installing new data measurement systems if necessary. The goal here is to develop a comprehensive understanding of the production process, identifying key factors such as dependencies, bottlenecks, and storage capacities. The analysis also covers the nature of the processes—whether they are continuous or batch processes—and involves mapping out the general production workflow through flow diagrams. Additionally, this task requires an evaluation of the general energy requirements associated with the process, including considerations of shift models and their impact on production.

1.2 Data Analysis

Following the general analysis, Data Analysis delves deeper into the temporal aspects of energy demand within the production process. This task focuses on understanding the temporal resolution of energy demands, identifying main energy consumers and energy peaks, and analysing demand patterns. A key component of this analysis is the correlation analysis, which seeks to identify the influence of various process parameters on the energy demand (in detail on aggregate level). This includes examining how factors like ambient temperature and product-specific requirements affect energy consumption. By understanding these dependencies, the analysis provides insights into how energy demand fluctuates and what factors drive these changes.

Subsequently, it must be assessed which data is important for modeling and which is important for the operation of the forecasting model. Furthermore, it must be assessed which data is available in which form and whether it can also be retrieved automatically from another application.

1.3 Process Modelling

The final task in the Foundation phase is Process Modelling. In this task, the process is modeled using either first principles modelling or data-driven approaches, or a combination of both, depending on the needs of the project. Traditional modelling methods include thermodynamic or mathematics- and physics-based approaches, which rely on established scientific principles to simulate the process. On the other hand, data-driven modelling involves the use of machine learning techniques, which can provide more adaptive and potentially more accurate models based on large datasets. A critical decision in this task is determining the necessary level of detail required for the model, balancing the complexity of the model with the accuracy needed for effective decision-making.

Together, these tasks in the Foundation phase establish a solid base for the subsequent phases, ensuring that the DSM DSS system is built on a comprehensive understanding of the production process, its energy demands, and the most appropriate modelling approach.

2 Development

The Development phase is where the foundational work transitions into actionable insights and tools that will drive the DSM DSS system.

2.1 Flexibility Analysis

The Flexibility Analysis focuses on identifying potential flexibility within the industrial system at various levels, including the overall system, specific process chains, and individual aggregates. The goal is to determine which processes or aggregates can be operated flexibly, and to classify the type of flexibility available—whether it involves power regulation, time-shifting operations, or switching fuels. The analysis also considers the duration of this flexibility and its potential impact on other parts of the process. For example, operating an aggregate flexibly might influence the timing or efficiency of other linked processes. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing strategies that maximise energy efficiency while minimising disruptions to production.

2.2 Functionality Development

This task involves the design and implementation of specific DSM measures tailored to the industrial setting. These measures are informed by the earlier data analysis, process modelling, and flexibility analysis. Potential functionalities include improving energy efficiency (a permanent measure), optimising

the timing of energy use (mid-term), and participating in market demand response (mid- to short-term). Some key functionalities are mentioned here: energy monitoring to detect real-time issues related to elevated energy demand, an interactive "what-if" tool for simulating different energy demand scenarios, and tools for enhancing energy efficiency through improved production scheduling. Additionally, functionalities can be designed for optimal scheduling that accounts for time-dependent, volatile energy prices, and unit commitment strategies such as fuel switching. Other possibilities include providing recommendations on how to purchase energy cost-effectively to meet demand. These functionalities can be applied to individual aggregates or entire process chains. Moreover, the potential exists to evolve these functionalities into a digital twin, enabling not just decision support but also direct control of the processes.

3 Application

3.1 Tool Requirements

This task outlines the specific data and IT infrastructure needed for the tool's implementation. It covers the type and format of data required, the necessary temporal resolution, and the existing IT infrastructure at the industrial site. Key considerations include how the data are stored, how the tool will access these data, the type of database to be used, and whether existing interfaces are adequate or new ones need to be developed. Additionally, the input data requirements for different functionalities are assessed, alongside the hardware needs at the industrial site to run the tool effectively. Moreover, for an automated operation of the tool, it must also be capable of recognising downtimes, such as weekends and holidays, to ensure accurate scheduling and functionality.

3.2 Tool Implementation

Task 3.2 focuses on establishing how the development team will access the industrial site's systems during the implementation phase. This could involve setting up VPN access or determining whether physical on-site presence is necessary. The implementation phase ensures that the tool is fully integrated into the industrial environment, enabling its functionalities to operate as designed.

3.3 Test & Validation Phase

Task 3.3 is characterised by multiple feedback loops, designed to iteratively refine and enhance the tool's overall performance. During this phase, the tool's functionalities are rigorously tested in real-world conditions, with continuous feedback informing improvements. This iterative approach ensures that the DSM DSS system is not only functional but also optimised for the specific needs and constraints of the industrial setting.

4 Timing and Duration

The development of the DSM DSS system is structured around six key milestones, each representing a critical phase in the progression of the project. The timing of each work task within the 3 main project phases (foundation, development and application) is flexible and highly dependent on the specific use case, considering factors such as the complexity of the developed DSM DSS system, the scope of DSM functionalities, the interaction with the production process, the status of the existing digital infrastructure, and data availability and accessibility. Consequently, we have specified a time span for each task rather than a fixed duration.

The process begins with phase 1, which focuses on the foundation of the system. Here, the Process Analysis (Task 1.1) spans 4 to 6 months, ensuring that a thorough understanding of the existing

processes is achieved. Following this, the Data Analysis (Task 1.2), lasting 2 to 4 months, is conducted to gather and prepare the necessary data. These two tasks are prerequisites for the Process Modelling (Task 1.3), which takes between 10 to 14 months. It's essential to complete the process and data analyses before starting the Flexibility Analysis (Task 2.1) in phase 2, which also takes 4 to 6 months. This sequence ensures that all necessary data is available for the flexibility assessment.

Phase 2, the development phase, begins in parallel with the Process Modelling (Task 1.3). This overlap is strategic, allowing for any findings from the flexibility analysis to be integrated into the ongoing process modelling. Once the flexibility analysis is underway, phase 3 (Application) can also commence to determine the specific requirements for the tools that will support the DSM functionalities. As Process Modelling (Task 1.3) progresses and a shared understanding of the process models is established, the development of DSM functionalities begins. Tasks 2.2 to 2.x involve the Functionality Development of these features, with each functionality requiring 4 to 6 months, depending on its complexity. These functionalities may include energy monitoring, what-if analysis tools, or operation optimisation approaches. Importantly, the Tool Requirements (Task 3.1) phase extends over 6 to 12 months, and it evolves in tandem with the development of functionalities to ensure a seamless implementation.

Finally, Phase 3 culminates with the Tool Implementation (Task 3.2), taking 3 to 4 months, followed by a Test & Validation Phase (Task 3.3) that spans a minimum of 6 months. This comprehensive testing phase is critical to validate the entire DSM DSS system and ensure that it meets all specified requirements.

In summary, the overall project spans a period from approximately 2.5 to 3.5 years, depending on the scope, data availability and complexity of the integrated DSM DSS system. The timeline is structured to allow for flexibility and adaptation as the project progresses, with a clear emphasis on parallel processing and iterative development to achieve a robust and well-integrated DSM DSS system.

Figure 2: Timetable for DSM DSS-system project